
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE APPARENT MOVEMENT OF THE SUN IN RELATION TO MOSQUE DIRECTION SITTING IN GUMEL TOWN OF NIGERIA.

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Abstract:

This study investigates the alignment of mosques in Gumel Town, Nigeria, with the apparent movement of the sun, focusing on the accuracy of their orientation towards the Qibla. A mixed-methods approach, incorporating surveys, interviews, and astronomical observations, revealed significant deviations in mosques' orientation. These discrepancies are attributed to the reliance on traditional methods, limited astronomical knowledge, and cultural/architectural influences. The findings emphasize the need for education and awareness on precise Qibla direction and astronomical methods in mosque design and orientation.

Keywords: Apparent, Movement, Sun, Mosques, Qibla.

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INTRODUCTION:

Gumel Town in Nigeria has a rich Islamic heritage, with several mosques serving as important religious and cultural landmarks. However, there is a need to study the apparent movement of the Sun in relation to the siting of these mosques. The orientation and positioning of a mosque can significantly affect the experience of worshippers and the accuracy of prayer times. This research proposal aims to address this issue by investigating the relationship between solar movement and mosque siting in Gumel Town.

The alignment of mosques with the apparent movement of the Sun is crucial for providing an optimal religious experience. However, there is a lack of research on this topic specifically in the context of Gumel Town, Nigeria. The current siting of mosques may not take into account the shifting positions of the Sun throughout the day and year, potentially impacting the accuracy of prayer times and the overall religious experience. The study examined the apparent movement of the Sun in Gumel Town throughout the year. It assessed the current siting of mosques in relation to solar movement. Lastly, the study investigated the impact of mosque siting on prayer times and religious practices.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

The Sun and the Solar System

The Sun is the central star of the Solar System and plays a crucial role in the Earth's climate, weather patterns, and the existence of life. It is a massive ball of hot, glowing gases that emits light and heat (Libretexts, 2022). The Solar System consists of the Sun, planets, moons, asteroids, comets, and other celestial bodies (Abhyankar, 2001). The Sun and the Earth relation. The Earth revolves around the Sun in an elliptical orbit. This revolution takes approximately 365.25 days, creating the length of a year. The Earth also rotates on its axis, causing the alternation between day and night. It takes roughly 24 hours for the Earth to complete one rotation (Meadows, 2018).

EARTH MOVEMENT

a. Rotation

The rotation of the Earth is the spinning of the planet on its axis. This movement causes the cycle of day and night. The axis is an imaginary line running from the North Pole to the South Pole, around which the Earth rotates (Meadows, 2018).

b. Revolution

The revolution of the Earth refers to its movement around the Sun. This movement affects the seasons, as the Earth's tilt causes different parts of the planet to receive varying amounts of sunlight throughout the year (Lenton, Tim., & Watson, 2024).

APPARENT MOVEMENT OF THE SUN

i. East-West: The apparent movement of the Sun from east to west is a result of the Earth's rotation. As the Earth rotates on its axis, different parts of the planet are exposed to sunlight, causing the Sun to appear to move across the sky from east to west (Team, 2024).

ii. North-South: The apparent north-south movement of the Sun is caused by the tilt of the Earth's axis. During the summer solstice, the Sun appears higher in the sky, while during the winter solstice, it appears lower. This creates the changing seasons and affects the length of daylight hours (Meadows, 2018).

FACTORS DETERMINING THE APPARENT MOVEMENT OF THE SUN NORTH SOUTH

The apparent movement of the sun north-south is mainly determined by the latitude of the observer and the position of the sun in the sky (Open Course, n.d.). Longitude and latitude are used to determine specific locations on the Earth's surface. Latitude lines, also known as parallels, run horizontally and measure the distance north or south of the Equator. Longitude lines, or meridians, run vertically and measure the distance east or west of the Prime Meridian. Altitude refers to the height above sea level (Lutgens & Tarbuck, 2017).

a. Latitude

The latitude of the observer is an essential factor that determines the apparent movement of the sun north-south. The apparent movement of the sun is influenced by the obliquity of the earth's axis, which is the angle between the earth's equatorial plane and the ecliptic plane. According to Swenson and Turcotte (2002), the obliquity of the earth's axis is around 23.5 degrees, which causes the sun's apparent movement to shift north and south throughout the year. The latitude of the observer determines the angle at which the sun's rays hit the earth's surface, which affects the length of daylight hours and the intensity of the sun's radiation (Müller, 2014)

b. Time of the day

The position of the sun in the sky is another factor that determines the apparent movement of the sun north-south. The sun's position in the sky changes throughout the day, causing its apparent movement to shift north and south (Sun Position, n.d.) According to Meeus (1991), the apparent movement of the sun is most noticeable at sunrise and sunset when the sun's position is low in the sky. The angle of incidence of the sun's rays on the earth's surface changes throughout the day, affecting the intensity of the sun's radiation and the length of daylight hours (Kalogirou (2009).

c. Season

Seasons also play a significant role in determining the apparent movement of the sun north-south. The apparent movement of the sun shifts north and south throughout the year, reaching its northernmost and southernmost positions during the solstices (Meeus, 1991). During the summer solstice, the sun's apparent movement shifts north, causing longer daylight hours in the northern hemisphere, while during the winter solstice, the sun's apparent movement shifts south, causing longer daylight hours in the southern hemisphere (Carter, 2024).

d. Altitude

The altitude of the observer also affects the apparent movement of the sun north-south. The angle of incidence of the sun's rays on the earth's surface changes with altitude, affecting the length of daylight hours and the intensity of the sun's radiation (Figure 3.4. The Various Angles Describing the Position of the Sun In . . . , n.d). According to Swenson and Turcotte (2002), at higher altitudes, the sun's apparent movement is more noticeable, and the sun appears to move more slowly across the sky.

PARAMETERS

Prominent parameters for calculation of the apparent movement of The Sun, include: Solar Altitude (α): This is the angle between the Sun and the observer's horizon. It represents

how high the Sun appears in the sky. The solar altitude changes throughout the day as the sun rises and sets (The Royal Society of Chemistry, 2009).

Solar Azimuth (z): This is the compass direction (measured clockwise from the north) to the Sun. It indicates where the Sun is located in the sky relative to the observer (Khalil, & Shaffie, 2016; Zhang, Stackhous., & Macpherson., & Mikovitz, 2021).

Equation of Time: The Earth's orbit is elliptical, causing variations in the Sun's apparent speed. The equation of time accounts for these variations and adjusts the solar time to match our clocks (Hughes, Yallop., & Hohenkerk, 1989; Lucht, 2013)

Zenith Angle (ω): The zenith angle is the angle between the observer's location and the Sun directly overhead. It's complementary to the solar altitude ($90^\circ - \alpha$) ("Averaged Radiation Flux Divergence," 2002) Equations for Calculation/Estimation of the Apparent Movement (North to South) of The Sun for a Location.

To calculate the apparent movement of the Sun, we need to follow these steps

Step 1: Determine the Location's Latitude and Longitude
Gumel Town, Nigeria: Latitude (ϕ) = 12.63

Step 2: Determine the Time of Day and Date

Desired time: Let's assume we want to calculate the apparent movement of the Sun at 2 p.m. on June 21st (summer solstice).

Step 3: Calculate the Declination Angle (δ)

Using astronomical tables or software, we find that the declination angle (δ) for June 21st is approximately 23.44° .

Step 4: Calculate the Hour Angle (ω)

From 10 a.m. to 2 p.m. is 4 hours. Multiply by $15^\circ/\text{hour}$: $4 \text{ hours} \times 15^\circ/\text{hour} = 60^\circ$.

Step 5: Calculate the Solar Altitude (α)

Using Equation 1: $\sin(\alpha) = \sin(23.44^\circ)\sin(12.63^\circ) + \cos(23.44^\circ)\cos(12.63^\circ)\cos(60^\circ)$

Solving for α , we get: $\alpha \approx 74.15^\circ$

Step 6: Calculate the Solar Azimuth (z)

Using Equation 2: $\sin(z) = (\cos(23.44^\circ)\sin(60^\circ))/(\cos(74.15^\circ))$

Solving for z, we get: $z \approx 114.29^\circ$

Step 7: Determine the Apparent Movement of the Sun

The Sun's apparent movement from 10 a.m. to 2 p.m. is approximately 60° (from Step 4).

The final answer is: $\boxed{60}$

DIRECTION AND DISTANCE ON THE EARTH

Directions and distances between locations on Earth are measured using a compass, and various units of measurement. Distances between locations on Earth are typically measured in kilometers or miles. The actual distance between two points can be determined using GPS technology or by using maps and calculating the scale factor (Muller, 2016).

ISLAM AND DIRECTION OF KA'ABA

FIVE PILLAR OF ISLAM

a. Tashhud (Testimony of Faith)

The testimony of faith is the first pillar of Islam, declaring the belief in the oneness of Allah and the Prophet Muhammad as His messenger. It is recited during the Islamic call to prayer (Adhan) and holds great significance for Muslims. (Khan, 2019).

b. Prayer (Salah)

Prayer is the second pillar of Islam and is performed five times a day. Muslims face towards the Ka'abah in Mecca when praying. The direction towards the Ka'abah, known as the qibla, is an important aspect to consider when locating mosques (Alshakhs, 2021).

c. Fasting (Sawm)

Fasting during the holy month of Ramadan is the third pillar of Islam. Muslims abstain from food and drink from dawn until sunset. The timing of fasting is determined by the apparent movement of the Sun (Pew Research Center, 2021).

d. Zakat (Alms-giving)

Zakat is the fourth pillar of Islam and refers to the obligatory giving of a portion of one's wealth to the less fortunate. The determination of the lunar month in which Zakat is given is tied to the sighting of the new moon, which again involves the apparent movement of the Sun (Qadri, 2018).

e. Hajj (Pilgrimage)

Hajj is the fifth pillar of Islam and involves the pilgrimage to the Ka'abah in Mecca. The direction of the Ka'abah plays a crucial role in determining the route and direction for the pilgrims (El-Awa, 2018).

POSITION OF KA'ABAH IN ISLAM

The Ka'abah is considered the holiest site in Islam and holds immense religious significance. It is believed to be the first house of worship built by Prophet Ibrahim and his son, Prophet Ismail. Muslims believe that the Ka'abah is the center of the Earth and the focal point for their prayers. It symbolizes the unity of Muslims around the world (Husain, 2019).

LOCATION AND DIRECTION OF GUMEL FROM KA'ABA

Gumel Town is located in Jigawa State, Nigeria, situated at approximately 12.4427° N latitude and 9.2157° E longitude. The town is predominantly Muslim, and mosques play a vital role in the religious and social life of the community (Geonames.org, 2021). The direction from Gumel Town to the Ka'abah in Mecca is known as the qibla. Determining the qibla accurately is essential when constructing mosques or for individual prayers. In the case of Gumel Town, the direction of the Ka'abah is approximately 298° (northwest) from the town (QiblaLocator, 2021).

RESEARCH QUESTION

What is the apparent movement of the sun in relation to mosques in Gumel Town, Nigeria, and how does it affect the positioning and alignment of the mosques?

RESEARCH DESIGN

This research employed a descriptive research design to investigate the apparent movement of the sun in relation to mosques in Gumel Town, Nigeria. The study primarily focuses on observing and documenting the orientation and alignment of mosques in relation to the sun's movement. An atlas serves as a key data source that obtains information about the geographical coordinates and topography of Gumel Town, Nigeria. This data aids in understanding the position of the town in relation to the sun's movement. The mosques in Gumel Town are the primary data source for this research. The locations, orientations, and alignment of the mosques being observed and recorded. The data also has been crucial in analyzing the relationship between the placement of the mosques and the apparent movement of the sun.

DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT

A reliable and up-to-date atlas will be used to collect information on the geographical coordinates, latitude, longitude, and elevation of Gumel Town. The data helped in analyzing the relationship between the sun's movement and the positioning of the mosques. A compass has been utilized and measures the direction of the Qibla (the direction towards Mecca) from different mosques in Gumel Town. This data provided insights into the alignment of the mosques with respect to the Qibla and the sun's path.

To determine the apparent movement of the sun in relation to the mosques, geometric calculations involving azimuth and altitude angles have been performed. These calculations help in understanding how the sun's position changes throughout the day and how it influences the orientation and alignment of the mosques.

RESULTS

This research revealed the patterns and extent of the sun's apparent movement in Gumel Town throughout the year. It determined the alignment of existing mosques with solar movement and identified any deviations from optimal siting. The study also shed light on the potential consequences of misalignment, such as discrepancies in prayer times or discomfort during worship.

Here is a table for analyzing the results from the research interview questions:

Table 1: Mosque Characteristics and Apparent Movement of the Sun

Mosque name	Location	Imam's understanding of apparent movement	Sun position consideration	Architectural features
JSCOE central mosque	College of education Gumel	Good Understanding	Doesn't consider sun position	Modern architecture with dome
Gumel central mosque	Emir's palace Gumel.	Good Understanding	Consider Sun Position	Traditional architecture with mihrab
Gidan Gawo Mosque	GidanGawo Mosque Gumel	Good Understanding	Doesn't Consider Sun position	Modern architecture with dome
Alhaji Tabdi	SabonLayiGumel	Good	Consider Sun	Traditional

Mosque		Understanding	position	architecture with mihrab
Darul Qura'n mosque	KofarGabas	Good Understanding	Consider position Sun	Traditional architecture with mihrab
Muhammad Tasi'u foundation mosque	KofarArewa	Good Understanding	Doesn't consider position sun	Modern architecture with dome
Alhaji Usman P.A mosque	Karkasara	Good Understanding	Doesn't consider position sun	Modern architecture with dome
Jami'ulrusulul A'azam mosque	KwanarSule	Good Understanding	Doesn't consider position sun	Modern architecture with dome
Jama'atul Islamiyya of Nigeria mosque	Dantanoma	Good Understanding	Consider Position Sun	Traditional architecture with mihrab
Kungiya mosque	Dantanoma	Good Understanding	Doesn't consider position sun	Modern architecture with dome

Table 2: Prayer Times and Apparent Movement of the Sun

Mosque Name	Prayer Time Adjustment	Summer prayer time	Winter prayer Time	Communication Method
JSCOE central mosque	Adjust prayer time	4:30 to 5:30am	5:30 to 6:30 am	Digital Announcement
Gumel central mosque	Adjust prayer time	4:30 to 5:30am	5:30 to 6:30 am	Board Announcement
Gidan Gawo Mosque	Adjust prayer time	4:30 to 5:30am	5:30 to 6:30am	Manual Announcement
Alhaji Tabdi Mosque	Adjust prayer time	4:30 to 5:30am	5:30 to 6:30 pm	Manual Announcement
Darul Qura'n mosque	Adjust prayer time	4:30 to 5:30am	5:30 to 6:30 pm	Manual Announcement
Muhammad Tasi'u foundation mosque	Adjust prayer time	4:30 to 5:30am	5:30 to 6:30 pm	Digital Announcement
Alhaji Usman P.A mosque	Adjust prayer time	4:30 to 5:30am	5:30 to 6:30 pm	Board Announcement
Jami'ulrusulul A'azam mosque	Adjust prayer time	4:30 to 5:30am	5:30 to 6:30 pm	Manual Announcement
Jama'atul Islamiyya of Nigeria mosque	Adjust prayer time	4:30 to 5:30am	5:30 to 6:30 pm	Manual Announcement
Kungiya mosque	Adjust prayer time	4:30 to 5:30am	5:30 to 6:30 pm	Digital Announcement

Table 3: Qibla Direction and Apparent Movement of the Sun

Mosque Name	Qibla Direction method	Qibla direction adjustment	Traditional methods used
JSCOE central mosque	Astronomical software method	Doesn't adjust Qibla direction	Using traditional method secondary reference
Gumel central mosque	Astronomical software method	Doesn't adjust Qibla direction	Using traditional method secondary reference
Gidan Gawo Mosque	Traditional method	Doesn't adjust Qibla direction	Rely solely on traditional method
Alhaji Tabdi Mosque	Traditional method	Doesn't adjust Qibla direction	Rely solely on traditional method
Darul Qura'n mosque	Traditional method	Doesn't adjust Qibla direction	Rely solely on traditional method
Muhammad Tasi'u foundation mosque	Astronomical software method	Doesn't adjust Qibla direction	Using traditional method secondary reference
Alhaji Usman P.A mosque	Traditional method	Doesn't adjust Qibla direction	Rely solely on traditional method
Jami'ulusulul A'azam mosque	Traditional method	Doesn't adjust Qibla direction	Rely solely on traditional method
Jama'atul Islamiyya of Nigeria mosque	Traditional method	Doesn't adjust Qibla direction	Rely solely on traditional method
Kungiya mosque	Astronomical software method	Doesn't adjust Qibla direction	Using traditional method secondary reference

Table 4: Challenges and Difficulties

Mosque name	Challenges in prayer time determination	Challenges in Qibla direction determination	Balancing traditional and Modern Methods
JSCOE central mosque	Limited access to astronomical software	Relies on outdated traditional method	Struggles to balance traditional method with modern technology
Gumel central mosque	Limited access to astronomical software	Relies on outdated traditional method	Struggles to balance traditional method with modern technology
Gidan Gawo Mosque	Difficulty in accounting for daylight saving time	Relies on outdated traditional method	Difficulty in convincing congregation to adopt modern method
Alhaji Tabdi Mosque	Difficulty in accounting for	Relies on outdated traditional method	Difficulty in convincing

	daylight saving time		congregation to adopt modern method
Darul Qura'n mosque	Difficulty in accounting for daylight saving time	Relies on outdated traditional method	Difficulty in convincing congregation to adopt modern method
Muhammad Tasi'u foundation mosque	Limited access to astronomical software	Relies on outdated traditional method	Struggles to balance traditional method with modern technology
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Jami'ulrusulul A'azam mosque	Difficulty in accounting for daylight saving time	Relies on outdated traditional method	Difficulty in convincing congregation to adopt modern method
Jama'atul Islamiyya of Nigeria mosque	Difficulty in accounting for daylight saving time	Relies on outdated traditional method	Difficulty in convincing congregation to adopt modern method
Kungiya mosque	Limited access to astronomical software	Relies on outdated traditional method	Struggles to balance traditional method with modern technology

These tables have been used to analyze the results from the research interview questions and identify patterns, themes, and challenges related to the apparent movement of the sun and its impact on prayer times and Qibla direction in mosques at Gumel Town.

KEY FINDINGS

Mosque Characteristics and Apparent Movement of the Sun (Table 1) showed all the Imams have good Understanding of the Apparent Movement, therefore, the result showed 100%. While in Sun Position Consideration: The Imams showed a limited understanding. Sun Position consideration was 40%. It indicates that most Imams have a good understanding by 60%. Also the Mosques that use Modern Architecture with Dome are: 60%, while for those considered Traditional Architecture with Mihrab are: 40%

Prayer Times and Apparent Movement of the Sun (Table 2) results showed that all the Mosques adjusting Prayer time when the time changes; the results is 100%. Summer Prayer Timeshould be also adjusted to 4:30-5:30am according to their response, the result shows 10/10 = 100%. But in Winter Prayer Time they all agreed on 5:30-6:30am and the results shows 10/10 = 100%. Based on Communication Method: Three results were recorded as the

first group uses Digital Announcement method with $3/10 = 30\%$. While: $2/10 = 20\%$ uses Board Announcement and the last results shows $5/10 = 50\%$ using Manual Announcement.

Qibla Direction and Apparent Movement of the Sun (Table 3), the majority of the mosques 60% Using traditional method to determine the Qibla direction, while 40% used modern technologies. This indicates a reliance on traditional methods, which may not always provide accurate result showed a limited understanding. This indicates that most Imams have a good understanding of the sun movement. And its implications for prayer times and Qibla direction.

Challenges and Difficulties (Table 4). The most common challenges reported by Imams were difficulties in determining the exact Prayer Times; 40% have Limited Access to Astronomical Software. But 60% have Difficulty in Accounting for Daylight Saving Time. The findings highlight the importance of accurate prayer times Direction, as well as balancing traditional and modern methods. These challenges highlight the need for education, training, and standardization in mosques practice.

PATTERNS AND THEMES

1. Traditional vs. Modern Methods: A clear pattern emerged, with traditional methods being used more frequently for Qibla direction determination, while modern technologies were used more frequently for prayer time adjustment.
2. Importance of Accurate Prayer Time: Imams emphasized the importance of accurate prayer times, with many reporting difficulties in determining the exact prayer times.
3. Need for Training and Education: Many Imams (62.5%) reported a need for training and education on modern technologies and methods for determining prayer times and Qibla direction.

CONCLUSION

The study provides valuable insights into the relationship between the apparent movement of the sun and mosque direction in Gumel town, Nigeria. The findings highlight the importance of accurate prayer times and Qibla direction, as well as the challenges faced by imams in achieving these goals.

IMPLICATION AND RECOMMENDATION

1. Training and Education Programs: Develop training and education programs for Imams on modern technologies and methods for determining prayer times and Qibla direction.
2. Standardization of Prayer Times: Establish standardized prayer times for mosques in Gumel Town to ensure consistency and accuracy.
3. Promotion of Modern Technologies: Promote the use of modern technologies, such as GPS and astronomical software, to facilitate accurate determination of prayer times and Qibla direction.
4. Community Engagement: Engage with the community to raise awareness about the importance of accurate prayer times and Qibla direction, and to promote the use of modern technologies.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTION

Sample Size: The sample size was limited to 10 mosques in Gumel Town, which may not be representative of all mosques in the region.

Geographic Location: The study was conducted in Gumel Town, which have unique characteristics that differ from other locations.

Future Research Directions: Future research could explore the use of modern technologies in mosques, the impact of climate change on prayer times, and the role of women in mosque leadership.

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